

(ANTI)BULLYING KIT (EN)

CREATED BY L'ÉCOLE DES VALEURS WITHIN THE PROJECT HEARTGUARD –
EMPOWERING YOUTH AGAINST BULLYING

L'École des Valeurs

Inspiring young people to grow through values-based education

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L'École des Valeurs is a non-profit organization founded in Luxembourg in 2023, inspired by Școala de Valori from Romania, which has been promoting values-based education for over 14 years. The organization supports young people in their journey of self-discovery, continuous learning, and active citizenship.

L'École des Valeurs aligns with the European Union's priorities in education and is actively involved in Erasmus+ programs that encourage youth development through innovative, cross-border initiatives.

HeartGuard – Empowering Youth Against Bullying

Educational Resources for Teachers and Youth Workers

Erasmus+ Project

HeartGuard – Empowering Youth Against Bullying is an Erasmus+ project developed to prevent bullying among teenagers aged 13 to 16, using creative and emotional development methods. Through a combination of theatre-based techniques and emotional intelligence education, the project has generated a set of practical materials aimed at supporting teachers and youth workers in creating safe, empathetic, and inclusive learning environments.

The project is implemented in partnership with EnRoot, an NGO established in Dinant, France.

The (Anti)Bullying KIT includes:

HeartGuard (1) - The Bullying Environment: Training Kit

HeartGuard (2) - Questions on Bullying Situations: Awareness Kit

HeartGuard (3) - (Anti)Bullying Scenarios: Awareness Kit

Guidelines for educators and youth professionals (Upon request)

The materials were developed in collaboration with experts from Luxembourg and France, as part of the Erasmus+ initiative.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the ANEFORÉ Luxembourg. Neither the European Union nor the ANEFORÉ can be held responsible for them.

VALEUS

ROLES IN BULLYING

MOTIVATIONS, BEHAVIORS AND SIGNS OF BULLYING

SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

CHILD GROUP INTERVENTION

CLASSROOM INTERVENTION

COMMUNITY AND SCHOOL CONTEXT

INDIVIDUAL INTERVENTION FOR CHILDREN DISPLAYING BULLYING BEHAVIORS

INTERVENTION FOR THE CHILD WHO IS THE TARGET OF BULLYING

FAMILY INVOLVEMENT IN DEALING WITH BULLYING

SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

ROLES IN BULLYING

**HeartGuard: Empowering Youth
Against Bullying, Erasmus+ 2024**

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Board Game for Teachers, Teens and Parents

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Community and school

Combating bullying in the community and at school. Addressing anti-bullying at the whole-school level as well as tackling bullying in the community involves developing critical thinking skills as well as encouraging pro-active behaviors and courage in approaching open, serious and sustained discussions aimed at equity, inclusion and non-discrimination.

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Teachers and Parents

Anti-bullying teaching in schools and support for parents to help their children manage and deal with the bullying problems they face.

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The one who suffers the bullying and stays passive

The passive victim of bullying is the category of people who are victimized by other people, who do not exhibit bullying behaviour.

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The one who suffers bullying and bullies in turn

The victim-aggressor is the category of people who are bullied by others, but who in turn exhibit bullying behaviors towards others.

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The one who is Passive Witness - Bystander

A bystander is a person who sees or knows about bullying or other forms of violence happening to someone else and does nothing to address the unpleasant situation in which the bullied person finds themselves. They are usually witnessing the physical and/or cyber bullying in action, who are passive and watch, who video it and make it go viral ... and who do and say nothing in order to defend the bullied person.

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The one who is Supportive Witness - Upstander

An upstander is a person who chooses to support an assaulted, abused or harmed person, who acts to help the assaulted, who shifts attention and redirects the abuser away from the assaulted. It is the person who generally notifies an adult/authority who can intervene.

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

MOTIVATIONS, BEHAVIORS AND SIGNS OF BULLYING

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The one who bully

Is a person who is habitually cruel, insulting or threatening towards others whom they consider to be weaker, smaller or otherwise vulnerable.

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Motivation of the one who bully (1)

The desire to get attention, popularity and admiration from others (against the background of emotional emptiness/emotional imbalance), the need to prove that he/she is stronger than the "victim".

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Motivation of the one who bully (2)

Sense of control, power and influence he can exert over others based on his own observations. A strong need to fit in, a desire to be validated and accepted in the group of people with the highest popularity.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (1)

Frequently gets violent with other people.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (2)

Causes verbal and physical conflict with others.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (3)

Is frequently reprimanded or punished by teachers/institution.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (4)

Has extra money or new things/goods whose provenance he/she cannot explain.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (5)

Quick to blame other people.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (6)

Lies or denies what they have done.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (7)

Does not accept responsibility for what they have done.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (8)

Has friends who bully other people.

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Signs that a person has become a bully (9)

Always feels the need to win or to be the best at EVERYTHING (becoming aggressive if he loses, not accepting that he has lost).

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People who become targets of bullying show (1)

Poor social and emotional coping skills.

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People who become targets of bullying show (2)

Difficult sociability, greater difficulties in making friends.

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People who become targets of bullying show (3)

Fewer peer relationships.

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**People who become targets
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(4)**

More loneliness.

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**People who become targets
of bullying show
(5)**

Submissive behaviors.

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**People who become targets
of bullying show
(6)**

Low self-esteem.

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**People who become targets
of bullying show
(7)**

Anxiety.

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People who become targets of bullying show (8)

Low popularity.

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People who become targets of bullying show (9)

Feeling insecure.

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Reasons not to tell anyone about bullying (1)

Children feel ashamed and embarrassed: this is particularly the case for boys who have been taught by society to "be a man", "be strong", "don't complain to anyone".

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Reasons not to tell anyone about bullying (2)

They are afraid of revenge: the powerlessness and fear of the target children, the desire to stop the torture makes the situation particularly frightening.

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Reasons not to tell anyone about bullying (3)

They do not believe that adults can help them or they are afraid that adults will not take the problem seriously: "adults are busy" and children's problems are numerous. Often, when parents, teachers hear that a classmate is calling other children in the class bad names, they think it's not important. Sometimes it takes a long time before adults realize the seriousness of the problem. Many adults dismiss/ignore bullying as something that all children go through and it is best for the child to avoid the 'bully' or respond in kind.

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Reasons not to tell anyone about bullying (4)

I believe that it is normal to be abused: this attitude is particularly specific to children living in abusive environments.

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Reasons not to tell anyone about bullying (5)

They don't want to be labeled as "snitches" or "traitors".

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Signs that someone is being bullied (1)

Refusal to go to school or lack of interest in school. If your child finds reasons not to go to school, it is a sign that something is wrong.

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Signs that someone is being bullied

(2)

Low academic achievement. If the child is so afraid of someone that he can't think of anything except how he might avoid them, then he is certainly not able to pay attention to homework in class.

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Signs that someone is being bullied

(3)

Going a "long way" to school or home. Children will change their usual route to avoid contact with bullies if this happens on the way to or from school.

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Signs that someone is being bullied

(4)

Withdrawal/isolation from family, extra-curricular activities, spending all time in his/her room with the door locked or in a space isolated from the rest of the family. The shame and humiliation that comes from being constantly humiliated causes children to want to escape the pain of the humiliation and the only way for children is to hide in a safe place.

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Signs that someone is being bullied

(5)

The child who is frequently hungry, although they state that they were not hungry at lunch or did not have enough time for lunch. The canteen or location, where children have lunch, is often the site of bullying: so avoiding the canteen is a way of avoiding meeting the 'bully'.

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Signs that someone is being bullied (6)

Refusal or avoidance to talk about the day at school. Children are ashamed and humiliated, they are afraid that if they tell adults about humiliating situations, the adults will disrespect them or blame them for what happens to them.

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Signs that someone is being bullied (7)

The child's desire to suddenly change class or school.

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Signs that someone is being bullied (8)

Loss or tearing of clothes, loss or damage to objects shortly after getting them, bruising, and explanations are not consistent with the injuries.

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Signs that someone is being bullied (9)

Signs of digestive tract upset, headaches, sleep problems, etc. Stress causes cortisol release. Cortisol prepares the body to react by fight or flight. When the body is under stress for a long time, it begins to break down, immune system functionality is reduced, digestion or other bodily functions suffer and various somatic problems are triggered. Psychological problems such as panic attacks, depression, anxiety, etc. can also occur.

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

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Context intervention at school level (1)

Increase supervision in the places where bullying behaviors most frequently occur (sports fields, hallways, bathrooms, schoolyard).

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Context intervention at school level (2)

Establish classroom rules that clearly express what we expect a child to do in a peer interaction situation.

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Context intervention at school level (3)

Establish clear consequences for breaking each rule and consistently enforce consequences for the manifestation of bullying behaviors.

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Context intervention at school level (4)

To use rewards for children who have reactions that discourage bullying (standing up for a targeted child or asking an adult for help).

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Context intervention at school level (5)

To modify, through interventions in the whole class, the level of empathy, the attitude and the way of reaction of the peers who witness the situation in which a peer is a target of bullying (so that as many peers as possible take the defense of the peer who is a target of bullying or ask for help from someone who has more power - an adult).

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Context intervention at school level (6)

To change, through teacher interventions, the level of knowledge, empathy and attitude towards the targeted child, so that through their attitude they model his/her acceptance in the group of children. The teacher and the group of children play an important role in early schooling in terms of changing the status of the child 'nobody plays with'. In primary school, the isolation and marginalization of children who frequently show inappropriate behaviour in relation to the educational context (refusing to listen to adults' requests, avoiding interaction with other peers, preferring to play alone, frequently showing aggressive behaviour in everyday interactions) is a complex process that is largely influenced by the relationship that the teacher establishes with these children.

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School-based consequence intervention (1)

To work individually with the target child to change the mode of reaction that fuels the target behavior when the bullying situation is moderate in intensity and the child can practice the skills learned.

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School-based consequence intervention (2)

To work with the group of children in the class to change the reactions of bystander peers who directly fuel the bullying behavior by laughing instigating or watching in silence.

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Intervention methods in managing bullying behaviors (1)

Use of direct sanctions

In cases involving the physical injury of someone or in situations where other methods have not led to a positive outcome. (Bullying behavior continues).

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Intervention methods in managing bullying behaviors (2)

Bullying prevention by reinforcing bystander behavior to discourage bullying

When the school wants to discourage bullying behavior without involving counseling.

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Intervention methods in managing bullying behaviors (3)

Developing the target child's skills

In mild cases involving teasing or verbal bullying. When it is decided that the target child can be taught to cope with bullying situations, using social skills (assertive communication, paradoxical response).

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Intervention methods in managing bullying behaviors (4)

Mediation

When the children involved want to get help from a mediator. (Children who display bullying behavior rarely want to meet with a mediator).

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Intervention methods in managing bullying behaviors (5)

Remedial strategies

In cases where the child exhibits bullying behavior, the child comes to feel remorse and remorse for what he/she has done and is ready to take action to correct the situation.

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Intervention methods in managing bullying behaviors (6)

Support group method

Where the child initiates the bullying or the group of witnesses who have encouraged the bullying are prepared by meeting with a counselor, to cooperate in such a way that they contribute to the correction of the situation for the target child.

COMMUNITY AND SCHOOL CONTEXT

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Intervention methods in managing bullying behaviors (7)

Method of involving the parties

In the case of bullying it is manifested by several children, and through interview and support from a counselor each of the initiators is willing to help reduce the target child's discomfort.

COMMUNITY AND SCHOOL CONTEXT

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

SOCIAL AND EMOTIONAL LEARNING

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Responsible Decision Making (2)

Problem-solving also requires an evaluation of possible and likely consequences.

Youngsters who are both bullies and victims tend to be emotionally volatile and to react aggressively before thinking through the consequences (Pelligrini, 2002). Bullies may narrowly consider the positive short-term consequences of bullying for themselves, but are less likely to consider the negative consequences of their actions on others or on their own relationships over time (Arsenio & Lemerise, 2001).

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Five core categories of social and emotional skills (1)

Self-awareness

Accurately assessing one's feelings, interests, values, and strengths/ abilities, and maintaining a well-grounded sense of self-confidence.

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Five core categories of social and emotional skills (2)

Self-management

Regulating one's emotions to handle stress, control impulses, and persevere in overcoming obstacles; setting personal and academic goals and then monitoring one's progress toward achieving them; and expressing emotions constructively.

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Five core categories of social and emotional skills (3)

Social awareness

Taking the perspective of and empathizing with others; recognizing and appreciating individual and group similarities and differences; identifying and following societal standards of conduct; and recognizing and using family, school, and community resources.

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Five core categories of social and emotional skills (4)

Relationship skills

Establishing and maintaining healthy and rewarding relationships based on cooperation; resisting inappropriate social pressure; preventing, managing, and resolving interpersonal conflict; and seeking help when needed.

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Five core categories of social and emotional skills (5)

Responsible decision-making

Making decisions based on consideration of ethical standards, safety concerns, appropriate standards of conduct, respect for others, and likely consequences of various actions; applying decision-making skills to academic and social situations; and contributing to the well-being of one's school and community.

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Social and Emotional Learning (SEL)

These skills allow children to calm themselves when angry, initiate friendships, resolve relationship conflicts respectfully, and make ethical and safe choices.

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Self-Awareness and Self-Management Skills

Children need to recognize and manage their emotions in order to respond to conflict calmly and assertively.

In order to handle conflicts effectively, children need to be able to recognize when they are getting angry, and learn to calm themselves before reacting. Children who frequently bully others tend to have trouble managing anger and to strike out aggressively.

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Social Awareness

Children need to learn to be tolerant, appreciate differences and interact empathetically with peers.

Research suggests that children often lack empathy for the victims of bullying, and that they view being different from the social ideal, or social norm, as the cause of bullying (Swearer & Cary, 2007).

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Relationship Skills

(1)

Children need to learn to initiate and maintain friendships and other relationships.

Victimized children tend to have fewer friends, to only have friends who are also victimized, and to have more enemies than non-victimized children (Rodkin & Hodges, 2003). Many are socially withdrawn and lack confidence and skills in effectively interacting with peers (Pelligrini, 2002; Salmivalli, 1999). Because of their lack of peer support, victimized Social and Emotional Learning and Bullying Prevention 8 children are less likely to have other children come to their defense when they are bullied (Rodkin & Hodges, 2003; Slaby, 2005).

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Relationship Skills

(2)

Children need to learn how to resist social pressure to enable, encourage or directly participate in bullying and to actively defend victims.

Studies have revealed that when bystanders observe bullying, they spend most of their time either actively participating in the act or passively encouraging the aggressor by serving as an audience; less than one-quarter of the time do they try to assist the victim (O'Connell, Pepler, & Craig, 1999; Slaby, 2005).

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Relationship Skills

(3)

Children need to be able to ask for help from peers or other adults when needed.

Research suggests that victims and bystanders typically do not seek help from peers or adults when they are unable to solve the problem on their own (O'Connell et al., 1999). Self-identified victims are particularly likely to blame themselves for their victimization and to “suffer in silence” (Graham, Bellmore, & Juvonen, 2006).

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Responsible Decision Making

(1)

Children need to think realistically and solve social problems effectively and ethically.

Effective social problem-solving requires an accurate assessment of the situation. Research indicates that children who frequently bully tend to misinterpret social interactions as being more hostile, adversarial, or provocative than their peers do (Dodge, 1993). These children also tend to hold more supportive beliefs about using violence and are less confident about using nonviolent strategies to resolve conflict (Bosworth et al., 1999). Not surprisingly, these students' relationships with friends and family members tend to be fraught with conflict (Society for Research in Child Development, 2008).

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

CLASSROOM INTERVENTION

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**This type of intervention
targets a few very important
issues
(1)**

Structuring a context that provides predictability and safety for all children by establishing rules and consequences.

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**This type of intervention
targets a few very important
issues
(2)**

Raising the awareness of all children of the implications of bullying behavior.

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**This type of intervention
targets a few very
important issues
(3)**

Increasing empathy and developing positive attitudes towards peers who become targets of bullying.

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This type of intervention targets a few very important issues (4)

To develop children's ability to have reactions in the role of bystanders leading to the deterrence of bullying behavior.

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In any intervention process we start first with assessment. To do a classroom intervention we need to know (1)

What are the classroom rules and consequences regarding bullying behaviors (especially for primary school children).

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In any intervention process we start first with assessment. To do a classroom intervention we need to know (2)

What are the attitudes of the peers regarding the actors involved in the bullying situation (the initiator, the target and those who witnessed and did nothing) and their possibility to do something about it.

Attitudes are very important and often guide the behavior of witnesses in a bullying situation. This process of identifying the attitudes of children in the classroom can be done with the help of a questionnaire. You will find such a tool in the appendix.

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Classroom intervention using rules and consequences

The use of punishment provides the context for learning by observing and imitating behaviors in which children use abuse of power in relation to their peers. Sanctions/punishments that are not logically related to the misbehavior displayed by children do not lead to improvement.

In other words, the extent to which children can identify a logical link between what they receive when they have misbehaved and the behavior they exhibit needs to be made. If the learner cannot see the logic between what they have done and the consequence obtained, the learning potential is almost nil.

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**In early schooling in particular,
to change bullying behaviors it
is important that at the
classroom level
(1)**

Clear rules to express what behaviors are expected of children in a peer interaction situation.

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**In early schooling in particular,
to change bullying behaviors it
is important that at the
classroom level
(2)**

Clear consequences by which children who display bullying can repair the harm they have caused to others.

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**In early schooling in particular,
to change bullying behaviors it
is important that at the
classroom level
(3)**

Rewards for bystander peers who react appropriately and discourage bullying (stand up to the bullying child or seek help from an adult).

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**For a child who has a history of
victimization, the intervention considers
the following aspects (1)**

Breaking the identification with the helpless reaction associated with bullying.

INTERVENTION FOR THE CHILD WHO IS THE TARGET OF BULLYING

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

CHILD GROUP INTERVENTION

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The reactions of assistance and its impact on those involved in a bullying situation (1)

Children having fun based on what they see or hear. Laughter is a manifestation that reinforces bullying behavior.

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The reactions of assistance and its impact on those involved in a bullying situation (2)

Children who instigate from the sidelines.
They directly encourage the bullying
behavior.

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The reactions of assistance and its impact on those involved in a bullying situation (3)

Children who watch in silence. These children remain separate from the bullying situation, but encourage the bullying behavior by watching. A person exhibiting bullying behavior needs attention to assert status or show power.

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The reactions of assistance and its impact on those involved in a bullying situation (4)

Children who leave such a situation. Walking away is not as encouraging as the other behaviors described above, but it is also reinforcing in that it leaves the person who is hurt unable to cope alone without any support.

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A classroom intervention program is successful when there will be as many classmates as possible who will empathize with another classmate who is the target of bullying and choose through their reactions to discourage unfair treatment (1)

They will either feel able to confront the bully.

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A classroom intervention program is successful when there will be as many classmates as possible who will empathize with another classmate who is the target of bullying and choose through their reactions to discourage unfair treatment (2)

They will remove that person from the bullying situation and take them away from the bully.

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A classroom intervention program is successful when there will be as many classmates as possible who will empathize with another classmate who is the target of bullying and choose through their reactions to discourage unfair treatment (3)

They break the silence and ask a teacher to intervene. Bullying often takes place in the presence of other children, away from the eyes of adults.

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Children who passively witness bullying and do nothing to help a peer who is the target of bullying fall into four categories according to the reasons

(1)

Children who feel it is none of their business to get into other people's problems. "It's none of my business when someone I don't know gets into trouble;" "it's not nice to get into someone else's business"; "I'm just an observer"; "they should sort out their own problems"; "it's none of my business".

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Children who passively witness bullying and do nothing to help a peer who is the target of bullying fall into four categories according to the reasons

(2)

Children who are afraid of consequences. "I could end up in the injured person's shoes"; "if I get involved, something bad could happen to me"; "I would be scared if it happened to me"; "it could be embarrassing"; "I don't want to be a snitch and tell a teacher".

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Children who passively witness bullying and do nothing to help a peer who is the target of bullying fall into four categories according to the reasons

(3)

Children who think the target child needs to learn how to handle themselves in such a situation. "Most people know how to take care of themselves and sometimes those who are the target of bullying deserve to have it happen to them". The level of empathy towards the targeted child is low and these bystanders tend to blame the child for being victimized.

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Children who passively witness bullying and do nothing to help a peer who is the target of bullying fall into four categories according to the reasons

(4)

Children who believe that their intervention would be futile or make things worse. "No one will mind if I intervene".

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What can we do to use the strength of the group of children to change bullying behavior? (1)

A curriculum that includes whole class activities to sensitize children to the impact of bullying, develop appropriate response skills to discourage bullying, communicate and help each other.

This type of intervention is useful in both early schooling and adolescence.

1. For adolescents the involvement of all peers is the key to success.
2. Classroom-based intervention program aimed at increasing awareness of the bystander, increasing empathy for the victimized person, developing personal responsibility and personal self-efficacy to support the target child are some of the directions that can lead to success. When bystanders have the necessary tools (knowledge, attitudes and skills), they will make other choices instead of fueling bullying behavior.

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What can we do to use the strength of the group of children to change bullying behavior? (2)

Workshops with teachers and parents to help them recognize bullying behaviours (especially those of relational aggression, such as exclusion, spreading rumours, teasing) and to know the most effective ways they can support their children so that they, in turn, can manage them appropriately.

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How can we access compassion for children who initiate bullying? (1)

A tree does not choose the soil in which it will grow and the environment that will affect it. It will develop differently if it is growing in an open place, in the middle of a forest, in a sheltered valley or on the top of a hill where it is very exposed to strong winds. It will grow anyway, but in order to grow it will have to adapt. Like children, they don't choose the family and environment in which they will grow up. They adjust to the family group into which they are born and experience the bond with their family members as love, regardless of whether they are cared for or neglected.

INDIVIDUAL INTERVENTION FOR CHILDREN DISPLAYING BULLYING BEHAVIORS

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How can we access compassion for children who initiate bullying? (2)

The intervention for children who initiate bullying is long-term and aims at modifying those personal risk factors that lead to the development and maintenance of bullying behaviors.

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

INDIVIDUAL INTERVENTION FOR CHILDREN DISPLAYING BULLYING BEHAVIORS

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What are the action lines for individual intervention? (1)

Developing self-esteem.

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What are the action lines for individual intervention? (2)

Developing empathy.

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What are the action lines for individual intervention? (3)

Development of positive interaction skills
with others (initiating and maintaining
friendships, cooperation, managing envy
and jealousy, gaining status in the group
through performance or desirable
behavior).

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What are the action lines for individual intervention?

(4)

Practice group integration skills using prosocial strategies (problem solving, communication, compromise, negotiation).

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What are the action lines for individual intervention?

(5)

Restructuring the way of looking at the social world by having access to experiences that teach them that relationships are not only a source of suffering but also of comfort, that you can let your guard down and others will not take advantage of it to attack you.

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The proposed intervention directions are based on studies that have highlighted the personal risk factors that predispose children to frequent bullying behaviors

(1)

Have a style of perceiving bullying as the appropriate way to interact with others.

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The proposed intervention directions are based on studies that have highlighted the personal risk factors that predispose children to frequent bullying behaviors

(2)

Possess a low level of empathy.

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The proposed intervention directions are based on studies that have highlighted the personal risk factors that predispose children to frequent bullying behaviors
(3)

Feel powerful and confident when they use bullying instrumentally, expect to get positive results from this way of behaving (e.g., peer approval), and use numerous moral non-involvement mechanisms to justify their behavior.

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The proposed intervention directions are based on studies that have highlighted the personal risk factors that predispose children to frequent bullying behaviors
(4)

Perceive bullying as a functional behavior that brings certain benefits.

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Children who initiate bullying with no history of victimization, exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(1)

Attitudes and beliefs that favor bullying.

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Children who initiate bullying with no history of victimization, exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(2)

Low level of empathy.

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Children who initiate bullying with no history of victimization, exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(3)

Feeling entitled and superior.

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Children who initiate bullying with no history of victimization, exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(4)

Good social status in the group of children.

INDIVIDUAL INTERVENTION FOR CHILDREN DISPLAYING BULLYING BEHAVIORS

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Children who have a history of marginalization and victimization exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(1)

Poor social skills.

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Children who have a history of marginalization and victimization exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(2)

Low self-esteem.

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Children who have a history of marginalization and victimization exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(3)

Social information processing deficits.

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Children who have a history of marginalization and victimization exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(4)

Low social status in peer group.

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Children who have a history of marginalization and victimization exhibit bullying behaviours and present certain risk factors
(5)

Perceive bullying as a functional behavior that brings certain benefits.

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Children who initiate bullying and have a high level of social intelligence exhibit bullying behaviors and show certain risk factors
(1)

They place high value on dominance and power and often get it.

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Children who initiate bullying and have a high level of social intelligence exhibit bullying behaviors and show certain risk factors (2)

Even if they are not actually liked by many of their classmates, they may be perceived by peers as popular, powerful, cool.

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Children who initiate bullying and have a high level of social intelligence exhibit bullying behaviors and show certain risk factors (3)

They are central members in a group and have friends. Teens who are bullies prefer to hang out with people who exhibit similar behaviors. Membership in this group gives everyone an incentive for coercive behaviors.

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The profile of these children is very varied (1)

Some of them have had previous experiences of victimization and have learned that if they don't show others the strength they have to put others down, they are sure to end up on their knees.

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The profile of these children is very varied (2)

Others have very good social skills, but they also use power strategies to gain fame and status in their peer group. In this case being aware of the consequences of their own actions and learning a healthy way to feel powerful can be of real help.

INDIVIDUAL INTERVENTION FOR CHILDREN DISPLAYING BULLYING BEHAVIORS

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The profile of these children is very varied (3)

Other children have many experiences of marginalization in early childhood and have a major deficit in the area of interpersonal skills, coping with difficult situations, reward acquisition, respecting the limits of another person in an interaction.

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For a child who has a history of victimization, the intervention considers the following aspects (2)

Developing personal skills to deal appropriately with bullying situations.

- Assertive communication (especially in cases of moderate verbal bullying).
- Problem solving.
- Managing uncomfortable emotions (fear, shame, sadness).
- Practicing group integration skills.

INTERVENTION FOR THE CHILD WHO IS THE TARGET OF BULLYING

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For a child who has a history of victimization, the intervention considers the following aspects (3)

Developing personal autonomy.

INTERVENTION FOR THE CHILD WHO IS THE TARGET OF BULLYING

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For a child who has a history of victimization, the intervention considers the following aspects (4)

Developing personal self-efficacy (ability to cope with multiple life situations).

INTERVENTION FOR THE CHILD WHO IS THE TARGET OF BULLYING

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

INDIVIDUAL INTERVENTION FOR CHILDREN DISPLAYING BULLYING BEHAVIORS

**HeartGuard: Empowering Youth
Against Bullying, Erasmus+ 2024**

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**The proposed directions for
intervention are based on the
results of studies showing personal
risk factors that predispose to
victimization**

(1)

Low peer acceptance.

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**The proposed directions for
intervention are based on the results
of studies showing personal risk
factors that predispose to
victimization**

(2)

Difficulty establishing and maintaining
friendships.

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**The proposed directions for
intervention are based on the results
of studies showing personal risk
factors that predispose to
victimization**

(3)

Difficulty integrating into a group.

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

FAMILY INVOLVEMENT IN DEALING WITH BULLYING

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In the case of bullying behaviors that occur in milder forms, parents are only asked for help if the efforts made at school have not led to an improvement in the situation (1)

Parents, just like their own children, need to know how to handle such situations, how to communicate with their children on these issues.

FAMILY INVOLVEMENT IN DEALING WITH BULLYING

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In the case of bullying behaviors that occur in milder forms, parents are only asked for help if the efforts made at school have not led to an improvement in the situation (2)

Sometimes the teacher or school counselor is their only available resource. Therefore, if the school is going to ask parents for help, it is important first to provide them with the necessary support to understand bullying and know what to do to support their children in dealing with the situation.

FAMILY INVOLVEMENT IN DEALING WITH BULLYING

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In the case of bullying behaviors that occur in milder forms, parents are only asked for help if the efforts made at school have not led to an improvement in the situation (3)

Parents, especially in the case of children who display bullying behaviors, need support to learn how to guide their children so that they, in turn, learn how to gain respect and status in the peer group other than by humiliating and demeaning others. This task is often difficult for the families of these children to accomplish without specialist support, because much of the pattern of relationships the children have learned from interacting with people in their own families.

FAMILY INVOLVEMENT IN DEALING WITH BULLYING

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The more individual intervention is coupled with family and classroom intervention, the better the results and the faster the progress.

FAMILY INVOLVEMENT IN DEALING WITH BULLYING

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The parenting style of children who engage in bullying behaviors has the following aspects
(1)

Upbringing based on fear and domination (authoritarian, punitive and unsupportive parenting style).

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The parenting style of children who engage in bullying behaviors has the following aspects
(2)

Poor family monitoring.

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The parenting style of children who engage in bullying behaviors has the following aspects
(3)

Crisis situations and dysfunctional relationships between parents (parental divorce, alcohol abuse, conflict between parents, domestic violence).

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

ADDRESSING VALUES AND POSITIVE BEHAVIOUR FOR LEARNING IN ANTIBULLYING

**HeartGuard: Empowering Youth
Against Bullying, Erasmus+ 2024**

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Care and Compassion

Expresses concern for oneself and showing interest, concern and care for others.

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Fair go

It involves protecting the common good in which all people are treated fairly for a just society. It includes a commitment to pursue and protect the common good, in which all people are entitled to fair legal, social and economic treatment.

ADDRESSING VALUES AND POSITIVE BEHAVIOUR FOR LEARNING IN ANTIBULLYING

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Respect

Treating others with consideration and due respect. It includes equality, freedom and the rule of law. Reflects personal commitment to a multicultural and ecologically sustainable society in which everyone has the right to justice and a fair life.

ADDRESSING VALUES AND POSITIVE BEHAVIOUR FOR LEARNING IN ANTIBULLYING

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Responsibility - personal, social, civic and environmental

Responsibility for one's own actions, including the exercise of self-discipline; responsibility for one's own way of interacting and cooperating with others, in particular for resolving differences through positive, constructive, non-violent and peaceful approaches. It reflects a personal commitment to a multicultural and ecologically sustainable society in which everyone has the right to justice and a fair life.

ADDRESSING VALUES AND POSITIVE BEHAVIOUR FOR LEARNING IN ANTIBULLYING

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Understanding, tolerance and inclusion

Being included and including others, actively listening to others' thoughts and feelings and building mutual trust.

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Ethics and integrity

To act in accordance with generally accepted norms and/or standards of proper [moral] conduct or practice.

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Freedom

To enjoy all the rights and privileges of citizenship without unnecessary interference or controls. It includes defending the rights of others and ensuring a balance between rights and responsibilities.

ADDRESSING VALUES AND POSITIVE BEHAVIOUR FOR LEARNING IN ANTIBULLYING

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Excellence (doing your best)

To seek to achieve something noteworthy and admirable individually and collectively and to do your best for yourself and others.

ADDRESSING VALUES AND POSITIVE BEHAVIOUR FOR LEARNING IN ANTIBULLYING

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Honesty and trust

Being honest and truthful, being committed to finding and expressing the truth, demanding the truth from others and ensuring consistency between words and deeds.

ADDRESSING VALUES AND POSITIVE BEHAVIOUR FOR LEARNING IN ANTIBULLYING

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SCHOOL-BASED ANTI-BULLYING APPROACH

**HeartGuard: Empowering Youth
Against Bullying, Erasmus+ 2024**

HeartGuard (2) - Questions on Bullying Situations

**How would you describe a
rude human being?**

**How would you describe a
kind human being?**

**How would you describe a
mean human being?**

**How would you describe a
friendly human being?**

How would you describe a human being who carries out bullying actions?

**How would you describe a
caring human being?**

**How does a bullied human
being feel?**

**Nominate a colleague to act
in your place next.**

**What could you do if you see
a colleague being bullied by
another colleague?**

What is bullying?

**What should you do if you see a
colleague being bullied by
another colleague?**

**How could you help
someone who feels unsafe
in your group?**

**How could you manage
your negative emotions if
you are being bullied?**

**Why do some
colleagues/people bully?**

How do harassed colleagues react, especially in social contexts?

What impact does bullying have on the person being bullied in terms of how they learn?

**What impact does bullying
have on the behavior of
the bullied?**

What are the most common mood changes that occur in the life of the bullied?

What is the reason for the occurrence of bullying in your school?

What could be the bullying prevention activities in your school?

**What activities could be done
in your school in order to stop
the bullying?**

What is the age at which children/young people in your school are most bullied? By whom?

How is the bully different from the bullied?

Who is prone to bullying?

Just wait for your next round.

**What are the polite words
most often used when dealing
with others?**

Explain why it is important to wait your turn to speak and not to interrupt your interlocutor?

**What rules of table manners
have you learned at home?**

Why is it important to respect others (children of the same age, young people, adults, older people, etc.)?

Why is it necessary to learn to recognize bullying?

**What helps you to feel safe
in your school?**

How can you deal with bullying?

Why is it important not to show the person who bullies that they have upset you?

**If you are being bullied, why
is it important not to hit
back?**

**What are the most likely places
or situations where you are
likely to be an easy target for
persons who bully?**

What would be wise to do if you feel harassed?

Why is it essential to talk to someone if you have been harassed?

What impact does harassment have on the behavior of the person who harasses?

Have there been/are there situations when colleagues or friends have made/make mean comments about you?

**What is the most hurtful
nickname others have given
you?**

Has there been an occasion in the past when someone has made fun of you for the way you look or behave?

**How isolated do you feel in
your group of friends/school?**

**Has there ever been a time when
someone spread mean and/or
untrue rumors about you?**

**Have you ever been
intentionally excluded from
a group?**

**Have you ever felt that
someone you considered a
friend tried to control you?**

**Has anyone ever imitated
the way you talk or
behave?**

**Has anyone ever damaged
your property?**

**Have you ever been
physically assaulted by any
of your colleagues/friends or
girlfriends?**

**Skip 3 boxes forward and
answer that question.**

Do you have any fears about going to school or participating in any extracurricular activities?

**Have photos of you been
posted online that you
would never want to
share?**

**Has anyone ever pretended
to be you online?**

Have other people posted mean things about you online or made biased comments about what you have posted?

How can parents tell when their children are being bullied?

How could a parent help their bullied child?

How might parents whose children don't report bullying at home talk about it?

How could you help the person who bullies?

**How would you describe
someone who only observes
an act of bullying but does not
intervene?**

How would you describe a man who notices an act of bullying, and seeks to intervene to stop the bullying?

Why is it important to seek to help the person who bullies to stop bullying?

**Involve a colleague to answer
the following question
together.**

**How many times has someone
laughed at you, called you
names or insulted you?**

How many times has someone started a rumor about you and you disliked it?

**How many times have you
been pushed, shoved, bumped,
tripped or spat on?**

How many times has someone tried to get you to do something you didn't want to do, for example to give them money or something that belonged to you?

**How many times has someone
intentionally destroyed your
property?**

Has anyone ever intentionally prevented you from participating in certain activities/events?

How many times has someone used his/her phone, sms or the internet to send you offensive messages?

Why do you think that often the person who bullies and who shows an air of superiority over the person who suffers the bullying, is in reality very self-insecure?

What are the causes that lead to repeated bullying in schools?

**Have there been cases of bullying
at school by your teachers?**

Could the boundaries imposed in school/classroom by your teachers be mistaken by you as bullying authority?

Are there instances when one of your teachers has ganged up with students in the class against weaker children?

Why do some people resort to bullying?

**How could an
observer/spectator stop a
bullying situation?**

What could parents do to protect their children from bullying?

What could teachers and school support staff do to protect pupils from bullying at school?

**Who are the preferred targets
of the persons who carry out
the bullying?**

**Go back 7 boxes and then
answer that question.**

Have you ever been tempted to press just a few computer keys to ruin someone's reputation?

**Have you ever been shunned
by a classmate?**

Why would some children prefer to be physically bullied rather than to be called names?

Why do young people with poorer social skills become the targets of bullies?

What are the reasons why, because of their appearance, race or religion or even disability, someone can become the target of bullying?

How disappointing is it to see that your friends/colleagues just choose to observe how some colleagues treat others badly?

SCRIPT 1

FADE IN:

INT. SCHOOL HALLWAY – AFTERNOON

ELENA (15, wide-eyed, bubbly) walks hurriedly toward her next class. She cannot be late. Yet, as she approaches, she feels her feet getting heavier.

She stops in front of the door of the chemistry lab, hesitating at the threshold. Just one more step.

ELENA

(V.O.)

You can do this.

She takes a breath and crosses over.

INT. CHEMISTRY LAB - CONTINUOUS

It is a bright summer day, yet there is something in the air. Tension, uneasiness...fear? Her classmates murmur nervously as they take their seats.

DANIEL (15, bespectacled, shy), sits near the back and doodles in his notebook.

The bell RINGS. The door SLAMS open.

MR. KAPLAN (50s, stern), chemistry teacher, strides in. He's in his 50s, with a sharp, menacing glare and an air of superiority. The class falls silent.

MR. KAPLAN

Good morning, geniuses.

He smirks, looking around as if assessing prey. The students shift uncomfortably. Elena freezes in her seat. She avoids eye contact, gripping her pen tightly.

MR. KAPLAN (CONT'D)

Let's see who's gracing us with their brilliance today.

Mr. Kaplan does the roll call then makes a brief pause.

MR. KAPLAN (CONT'D)

Tim! Still shopping at the thrift store, I see.

TIM (15) adjusts his worn-out sweater. Mr. Kaplan's eyes land on BIANCA (15).

MR. KAPLAN (CONT'D)

Bianca, sweetheart, pass a brush in that hair. Do something with... that!

Bianca looks down.

MR. KAPLAN

Now.. Daniel! What's the molecular formula of ammonia?

Daniel freezes.

MR. KAPLAN (CONT'D)

Those eyes of yours... my goodness, do they always bulge like that, or are you just perpetually confused?

Daniel's face burns red. Elena glances at him.

MR. KAPLAN (CONT'D)

Anica.

ANICA

NH_3 , Mr. Kaplan.

MR. KAPLAN

Perfect, as always. See, Daniel? It's not that hard. Let's try again. What's the molar mass of water?

Daniel's hands tremble. He stammers, but nothing coherent comes out.

MR. KAPLAN

No? Doesn't ring any bells? Don't worry. You won't need chemistry when you are wiping tables at McDonald's. Sit down.

Elena jumps up.

ELENA

Mr. Kaplan, please don't speak to him like that!

The class goes silent. All eyes are on Elena, who is visibly shaking, but determined.

MR. KAPLAN

Speaking the truth can be unpleasant, Miss Lopez, but it is better to know your worth early. Then you won't be disappointed later when your life does not amount to anything. But it's OK. The world needs janitors and cleaning ladies, too.

(throws a rag at Daniel)

Might as well start practicing now. Wipe the board!

FEW WEEKS LATER

INT. SCHOOL AUDITORIUM - DAY

A small group of STUDENTS gathers around, finalizing preparations for a play. The chemistry teacher, along with OTHER TEACHERS and the PRINCIPAL, takes a seat in the audience, curious.

ON STAGE: A STUDENT dressed as Mr. Kaplan paces.

STUDENT

Ah, my favorite disaster zone! The worst class in the school.

The audience chuckles, recognizing the words. Mr. Kaplan shifts uncomfortably.

STUDENT

Tim! Did you find those clothes in a dumpster?

TIM (as himself)

What I wear doesn't define me. And it definitely doesn't make me less than anyone else. I am the youngest of three brothers raised by a single mother. All my clothes are hand-me-downs. I was so ashamed. I shouldn't have been. I've been teased before about my clothes, but it is different coming from you. You're an adult. You should know better.

The audience grows silent. Mr. Kaplan frowns.

STUDENT

Bianca! Ever considered smiling? Your face is so plain.

BIANCA (as herself)

I am so much more than my looks. Shouldn't I be valued for who I am?

The tension builds. Mr. Kaplan watches, expression unreadable.

STUDENT

Daniel! Your eyes make you look like a goldfish!

DANIEL (as himself)

Or maybe they just make me, me. Why should looking different mean I'm stupid?

A pause. The fake Mr. Kaplan looks at the class, but instead of silence, each student speaks up, echoing real responses.

ELENA (as herself)

You make us feel worthless, but we are not. We deserve respect.

STUDENT #1

You act like words don't matter, but they do. They stick with us long after class is over.

STUDENT #2

We come to school to learn, not to be torn down by someone who's supposed to guide us.

STUDENT #3

A teacher should inspire students, not humiliate them. Do you think mocking us makes us better? It just makes us afraid.

STUDENT #4

Maybe if you taught us with kindness instead of cruelty, you wouldn't call us the worst class. Maybe we'd actually want to learn. Now that you know how we feel, will it make a difference?

The real Mr. Kaplan shifts in his seat, face tense. The rest of the audience remains quiet, absorbing the weight of the moment.

FADE OUT.

SCRIPT 2

FADE IN:

INT. HIGH SCHOOL HALLWAY - DAY

LAVINIA (16, Romani heritage, kind, reserved) walks through the hallway, clutching her books. Whispers and giggles follow her. **IRINA** (17, haughty) and **MAX** (16, smug) lean against a row of lockers, smirking.

IRINA

Look, it's Lavinia. Did you bring your crystal ball today?

MAX

Or maybe she's casting a spell on us.

Lavinia lowers her gaze, gripping her books tighter. A **TEACHER** walks by but does nothing, barely glancing at the interaction. Lavinia swallows hard and walks into the classroom.

INT. CLASSROOM - LATER

Lavinia sits in her seat, silent. The teacher takes attendance and then opens a book.

TEACHER

Today we are going to discuss Tess D'Urberville. Now, in the old times, it was not unusual for young girls to marry and have kids in their teenage years. In some cultures, they still do today. I am sure Lavinia here could tell us more about it.

Snickers ripple through the class. Lavinia freezes. She grips her pencil, her knuckles white.

EXT. SCHOOLYARD - DAY

Lavinia sits alone on a bench, watching other kids laugh and play. Her face is awash with sadness and longing.

SANDRA (16, thoughtful, hesitant) approaches and sits next to her.

SANDRA

Hey, are you okay?

Lavinia looks up, surprised. They've spoken before, but never like this.

LAVINIA

I'm fine.

Sandra looks at the group of kids playing, then back at Lavinia.

SANDRA

That was really uncool, earlier, in class. I thought about saying something, but...

Lavinia looks at her, unsure.

SANDRA

I don't know how you stand it. I couldn't. I would lock myself in my room and never leave again really admire you.

LAVINIA

(touched)

Really?

SANDRA

You are so strong. And talented. I don't know why they can't see it.

Lavinia smiles, touched.

LAVINIA

Thank you.

INT. LAVINIA'S BEDROOM - NIGHT

Lavinia sits at her desk, writing an essay titled "**My Name is Lavinia.**"

INT. CLASSROOM - DAY

Lavinia stands in front of her classmates, essay in hand. The same students who once mocked her now sit in silence.

LAVINIA

“No one asked me if I wanted to be born, the color of my skin or my eyes or my hair. I couldn’t choose my family or my country, but my personality belongs to me. I love music. I can play the piano. I love to draw and mathematics. My favorite book and show is Anne with an E.

I had no choice in the skin I was born in, but I can choose the person I want to be. I dream of becoming an architect or a designer. But whatever I become, I will always try to treat others with kindness and respect and see them for what they truly are.

Thank you.”

She bows slightly and walks to her seat.

Sandra claps from her seat. Other students join in. Irina and Max shift uncomfortably. The teacher smiles, approvingly.

FADE TO BLACK.

SCRIPT 3

FADE IN:

EXT. HIGH SCHOOL COURTYARD - MORNING

LIAM, 16, sits in his wheelchair, watching students pass by. Some glance at him with pity, others with indifference. **CHLOE** and **JAKE**, two of his biggest tormentors, approach, smirking.

JAKE: Hey, wheels, ready for another day of rolling through life like a speed bump?

CHLOE: Maybe someone should put a "Caution: Slow Moving Vehicle" sign on your back.

They laugh.

Liam lowers his eyes but says nothing and pushes towards the classroom.

The BELL RINGS.

INT. BIOLOGY CLASSROOM - LATER

The teacher, **MR. HENDERSON**, a friendly middle-aged man, steps forward.

MR. HENDERSON: Alright, class. Let's see your presentations. Who wants to start?

Silence.

MR. HENDERSON: Liam?

Liam takes a deep breath and rolls to the front. He clicks his laptop, and the title of short film appears on the projector: **ANTS**.

LIAM: My project is a short film about ants. Ants are fascinating creatures with highly developed social structures, and their care for one another is a crucial aspect of their survival. They help each other, even those who are injured or sick. They work together to survive. Ants work together to defend their colony from predators and intruders. Some species, even engage in rescue missions, carrying injured nestmates back to the nest.

The video plays, showing a group of ants carrying a crippled ant. Some students snicker. Chloe and Jake exchange amused looks.

JAKE (whispering to Chloe): Maybe Liam should be an ant. At least they'd carry him around.

Chloe and Jake laugh. The professor looks over to them and they stop.

The video ends. The professor pats Liam on the shoulder.

MR. HENDERSON: Very good, Liam. Who's next? Dina!

Liam rolls over to his seat. As he passes Chloe and Jake...

CHLOE (whispering): A wheelchair and an ant? The perfect combo!

Liam swallows hard.

INT. SCHOOL HALLWAY - LATER

Liam wheels himself toward his locker, shoulders slumped. A voice calls out.

ALEX (O.S.) Hey, Liam!

Liam turns to see ALEX, one of his classmates, a confident student with a camera slung around his neck.

ALEX (CONT'D): I liked your film. It was really cool. I'm also working on a short documentary about the Sun Blasters. Ever heard of them?

LIAM: Yeah...! They're awesome.

ALEX: I need to upload before their upcoming concert next week and between class, homework, filming and editing I'm pretty swamped. Would you like to help?

LIAM: Umm? Really?

ALEX: Really.

LIAM: OK. Yeah!

ALEX: Texted you the address. Tonight at 7. Don't be late.

Liam hesitates, then nods slowly, still not fully believing what happened.

MONTAGE OVER SEVERAL DAYS:

- Liam films the band practicing, laughs with the band members.
- He edits footage late into the night, his eyes glued to the screen.

INT. SCHOOL HALLWAY – ONE WEEK LATER

Alex and Liam look at the final cut of the movie on a laptop.

ALEX: Liam, this is amazing. You've got serious talent. You should totally be part of my film crew.

Liam beams. Just then, Chloe and Jake walk by.

CHLOE: Aww, did Liam find a little friend to play pretend director?

Jake chuckles. Alex squares his shoulders.

ALEX: Really? What's wrong with you?

Dan, another colleague, stops by.

DAN: Did you guys see the new stories posted by the Sun Blasters? Liam, you're the dude.

He gives Liam a high five.

Chloe and Jake look at each other confused. They check their phones.

ALEX: Let's go Liam.

Liam and Alex walk away.

FADE OUT.

SCRIPT 4

FADE IN:

INT. HIGH SCHOOL HALLWAY - MORNING

LIAM, a 16-year-old student in a wheelchair, moves down the hallway, his hands gripping the wheels tightly. He keeps his head down, trying to avoid eye contact. **CHLOE** and **JAKE**, two notorious bullies, lean against a row of lockers, exchanging a mischievous glance as Liam approaches.

CHLOE: Oh look, it's Speed Racer. What's the rush, Liam? You've got a big film premiere today?

JAKE: Yeah, I hope it's not as boring as your last one. I almost fell asleep watching it.

Liam doesn't respond, just keeps moving. A few passing students chuckle at Chloe and Jake's remarks. Liam grips the wheels harder, his knuckles white.

INT. BIOLOGY CLASSROOM - LATER

The class is gathered, waiting for the presentations to begin.

MR. HENDERSON: Alright, class. Let's see your presentations. Who wants to start?

The teacher looks at Liam.

MR. HENDERSON: Liam?

Liam takes a deep breath and rolls to the front. He clicks his laptop, and the title of short film appears on the projector: **ANTS**.

LIAM: My project is focused on the functioning of ant colonies. How ants work together to support their own, even helping the sick and injured members.

The screen lights up with Liam's short film. The video shows ants carrying food, protecting one another, and assisting weaker ants. It's well-shot, well-edited, and deeply meaningful.

Liam finishes his presentation.

MR. HENDERSON: That was a fantastic presentation, Liam. The level of detail and the storytelling were impressive.

Liam nods in gratitude but barely smiles.

He rolls back to his seat. As he passes the first row of seats, he hears snickers.

CHLOE: Aww, so touching. Are you hoping we'll all carry you around like those ants, Liam?

JAKE laughs.

INT. HIGH SCHOOL HALLWAY - AFTER CLASS

ALEX, a senior and the head of the high school online newspaper, stands near a bulletin board, talking with DIAN, another student. Liam rolls up hesitantly.

LIAM: Hi, Alex. Umm, I was wondering... did my film make it onto the website?

Alex hesitates, exchanging a quick look with Dian.

ALEX: We decided to go with a different submission. Something more personal, more... human interest.

Liam looks away, his disappointment clear. CHLOE walks by, smirking.

CHLOE Wow, Liam. You really thought you were gonna be the next Spielberg, huh?

Alex shoots her a glare but doesn't say anything. Liam exhales, nods.

LIAM: Thanks for considering it.

Alex: Sure. Maybe next time.

Liam nods, sadly and rolls away.

INT. LIAM'S HOUSE - NIGHT

Liam is having dinner with his parents. He is absently stirring his food.

MOM (encouraging): You love making films, Liam. Don't give up.

LIAM: I tried. I'm not sure what else I can do.

MOM: I know it hurts, sweetheart, but you are just starting out. Show them what you can do.

DAD: Success isn't about how many times you get knocked down. It's about getting back up.

Liam sighs.

INT. LIAM'S BEDROOM - NIGHT

Later, in bed, Liam scrolls through Instagram absentmindedly, when a message catches his attention. It comes from the Natural History Museum.

MESSAGE: Hi Liam, we came across your insect videos and we loved them! Would you be interested in having them featured in our upcoming event?

Liam stares in disbelief.

INT. SCHOOL HALLWAY - ONE WEEK LATER

Liam rolls through the hallway. CHLOE and JAKE are leaning against the lockers, as always.

CHLOE Hey, Spielberg. How's the filmmaking?

LIAM: Good, great. Thank you for asking.

Chloe and Jake are taken aback by Liam's answer. This time, there's something different in his demeanor.

INT. CLASSROOM - MOMENTS LATER

The professor stands at the front of the class.

PROFESSOR: Before we begin today's lesson, I just wanted to take a moment to congratulate Liam. His insect videos were featured at the Natural History Museum event this week, and it was a huge success! Good going, Liam! We are proud of you.

The class murmurs in surprise. Everyone checks their phones.

Liam glances at Chloe and Jake. For the first time, they have no snarky comeback.

Liam takes in the reaction, a small but victorious smile appearing on his face.

FADE OUT.

SCRIPT 5

FADE IN:

INT. HIGH SCHOOL – SCHOOL HALLWAY – MORNING

ALEXIA stands in front of a bulletin board, carefully pinning up a campaign poster. It reads: “Vote Alexia for Student Council President! Leadership. Integrity. Change.” She steps back to admire her work.

Sam, one of her Alexia’s friends and classmates nods approvingly.

SAM: Looks good! You got this, Alexia.

ALEXIA (nervous, but excited): I’m still not sure, but... Why not, right? We can make a difference.

(hey walk away. A few moments later, MIRA and her FRIENDS approach. MIRA smirks, pulls out a marker, and draws devil horns on Alexia’s face on the poster.

MIRA (mocking): Leadership. Integrity. Change. More like Loser. Invisible. Cringe.
Her friends laugh as they walk away.

SCENE 2 – SCHOOL HALLWAY – NEXT DAY

Alexia stares shell-shocked in front of her posters—they’re all defaced. Some have mustaches drawn on her face, others have insults like “Stupid” and “Ugly” scribbled over them. She takes a deep breath. Her phone buzzes. She check it to find another hateful comment on her social media: “No one wants an ugly loser like you as president.” More notifications flood in.

SAM (concerned): Alexia... this is getting bad. Maybe you tell the headmaster.

ALEXIA : I’ll talk to her.

SCENE 3 – SCHOOL CAFETERIA – AFTERNOON

The cafeteria is buzzing with students. Laughter, trays clattering, conversations overlapping. ALEXIA, holding her lunch tray, scans the room until she spots MIRA sitting at a table with her FRIENDS.

ALEXIA takes a breath and marches toward them. Students around the cafeteria begin to take notice, sensing tension in the air.

ALEXIA (firm, controlled): Mira.

Mira looks up with a smirk.

MIRA (mocking surprise): Alexia! To what I owe the honor?

ALEXIA: I know it's you. The posters. The messages.

Mira raises an eyebrow, glances at her friends, then lets out an exaggerated laugh.

MIRA: Whoa, whoa, whoa. Accusations? Without proof? That's defamation. Maybe I should sue.

Her friends chuckle. ALEXIA sets her tray down on the table, leaning in.

ALEXIA (whispering): Why are you doing this?

Mira leans forward too, their faces inches apart. Her smile doesn't reach her eyes.

MIRA (sweetly, mockingly): Because it's fun. And because I can.

Alexia stiffens. Mira takes a sip of her soda, looking unbothered.

MIRA : Face it, Alexia. You're not up to the task. You never were. These are the big leagues for exceptional players. You can't compete, you don't have what it takes.

She leans back, crosses her arms.

MIRA (louder): Don't blame me if no one likes you. Some people are just meant to amount to anything.

The whole table laughs as Alexia clenches her fists. She grabs her tray and walks away, head high, but inside, she's breaking.

SCENE 4 – ALEXIA'S BEDROOM – NIGHT

Alexia sits on her bed, knees to her chest, staring at her laptop screen. Her phone buzzes again. Another notification. Another message.

She hesitates, then opens Instagram. Her stomach drops. A new post—photos of her, edited and fake. They make her look like she's shoplifting, cheating on a test, even in a mugshot. Dozens of cruel comments underneath.

COMMENT 1: “Didn’t know our future president was a criminal 😬”

COMMENT 2: “Trash like this should be expelled.”

COMMENT 3: “LMAO look at her face, no wonder she has no friends.”

Her breath comes in shallow gasps. Her fingers tremble as she locks her phone. She swallows hard and picks it up again, dialing her mom.

MOTHER (answering, tired, background noise of hospital beeping and chatter): Hey, sweetheart, I can’t talk long. What’s up?

ALEXIA (small voice): Mom... I—something’s happening at school.

MOTHER (distracted, sighing): Alexia, I know it’s tough, but I have a twelve-hour shift. Can we talk later?

ALEXIA: Umm... sure.

MOTHER (cutting in, exhausted): I love you, honey. We’ll talk tomorrow, okay?

Click. The line goes dead. Alexia grips her phone, staring at it. A long pause. Then, she tosses it onto the bed, her eyes stinging with tears.

She looks back at her laptop. Slowly, she types: “How to report cyberbullying?” She clicks on a website, scrolls... her eyes scanning Her fingers hesitate over the keyboard. Finally, she takes a deep breath and starts typing.

SCENE 5 – PRINCIPAL’S OFFICE – DAY

ALEXIA sits in front of PRINCIPAL WARD, who is flipping through papers. MIRA sits across from her, arms crossed, feigning innocence.

PRINCIPAL WARD (sighs, rubbing his temples): Alexia, you’ve made serious accusations against Mira. You say someone has been spreading fake photos and sending you hateful messages?

ALEXIA (frustrated): It’s not just messages. They ruined my campaign posters, they—

MIRA (interrupting, gasping dramatically): This is awful. But Principal Ward... I’ve been getting messages too.

(She pulls out her phone, swipes, then hands it over. On the screen are threatening messages that appear to be from Alexia.)

MESSAGE 1: "I swear to God, Mira, you'll regret this."

MESSAGE 2: "You better watch your back."

MESSAGE 3: "I will destroy you."

(Alexia's jaw drops.)

ALEXIA: I—what?! That's not me! Those are fake!

Mira sniffles, faking sadness.

MIRA: I just don't get why you hate me so much, Alexia. I thought we were just running fair campaigns. But this... this is too much.

Principal Ward looks at Alexia, unimpressed.

PRINCIPAL WARD (firmly): Alexia, do you have proof to support your claims?

Alexia freezes. She knows Mira is lying, but she has nothing to prove it. Mira smirks, just slightly.

ALEXIA (small voice): I... I don't.

PRINCIPAL WARD (sighing, shaking his head): Without evidence, I can't take sides. You two need to focus on your campaigns and stay away from each other. Alexia, if those messages are really from you, you could face suspension. I will look into it.

Alexia's fists clench. She wants to scream, to fight back. But she sees Mira's victorious expression, and her stomach sinks.

Principal Ward stands, signaling the meeting is over. Mira grabs her bag, winking at Alexia before walking out.

Alexia sits across from the PRINCIPAL. Mira sits nearby, arms crossed, pretending to look innocent.

SCENE 6 – ALEXIA'S ROOM – NIGHT

Alexia sits at her desk, hands clenched into fists. Her laptop screen glows in the dim room. She opens her email and stares at the anti-bullying organization's reply.

EMAIL RESPONSE:

"We can help. Start by gathering evidence—screenshots, timestamps, witness statements. Save everything. Build your case."

Alexia's lips press together. She opens her phone, begins scrolling, screenshotting every message, every post, every comment. She digs deeper, checking usernames, timestamps, metadata. Every single clue she can find.

Her eyes burn from staring at the screen, but she doesn't stop. She sets up a private folder, saves files. The clock ticks past midnight.

She exhales, looking at the mountain of evidence she's compiled, then sends it all by email. A slow, determined smile spreads across her face.

ALEXIA (whispering to herself): Let's see you deny it now, Mira.

SCENE 7 – PRINCIPAL'S OFFICE – TWO WEEKS LATER

The air in the office is thick with tension. ALEXIA sits in one chair, her back straight, fingers gripping the edge of her seat. Across from her, MIRA lounges in her chair, her legs crossed, looking bored. PRINCIPAL WARD flips through papers, oblivious to the silent battle happening between the two girls.

PRINCIPAL WARD (clears throat): I called you both here again because the situation has escalated. More complaints have come in—anonymous reports from students. I want to resolve this once and for all.

MIRA (fake concern, shaking her head): I totally agree, Principal Ward. This has been so stressful. I'm just trying to run a clean campaign, but Alexia keeps dragging my name through the mud. It's really sad, honestly.

She glances at Alexia, a sly smile playing at her lips. Alexia doesn't react.

PRINCIPAL WARD (folding his hands together): Alexia, last time we spoke, you made some serious accusations, but you didn't provide enough evidence. If you don't have anything new, I'm afraid this discussion is over.

A pause. Then—A KNOCK AT THE DOOR. The tension in the room spikes.

The door opens. ALEXIA stands, turns, and steps aside as a sharply dressed WOMAN in her mid-30s walks in, holding a thick folder. She nods politely at the principal before setting the folder down on the desk with a heavy thud.

MIRA (laughing nervously): This is ridiculous. Alexia's just mad because she's losing the election. She'll do anything for attention.

Natalie opens the folder and begins spreading out papers, printed screenshots, and transcripts. Alexia watches Mira's smile slowly disappear.

NATALIE (calmly): What's ridiculous is how much effort went into harassing Alexia online. We've compiled records of dozens of anonymous messages sent to her social media, all traced back to accounts linked to Mira's friend group. Some of them were created with school emails—very sloppy. With other things you were more creative, but you are not as smart as you think you are.

Mira stiffens. Principal Ward frowns, flipping through the documents.

PRINCIPAL WARD (shaking his head, sternly): This... this is serious, Mira.

MIRA (voice rising, defensive): You believe this? You're just going to take Alexia's side? Again—where's the proof that I did anything? I didn't tell anyone to post those things. You can't pin this on me.

ALEXIA (leaning forward, voice sharp): You're right, Mira. You never directly posted anything. But you didn't have to.

She picks up a sheet from the folder, holds it up. It's a private group chat screenshot.

ALEXIA (mocking Mira's words from the cafeteria weeks ago): "Because it's fun. And because I can."

Mira's face goes pale.

Principal Ward stares at the screen, his jaw tightening. Natalie slides forward another sheet—this one showing timestamps linking Mira's student account to multiple anonymous messages.

NATALIE (calm, but firm): Encouraging others to bully someone is just as serious as doing it yourself, Mira. And these accounts? They were traced back to the school's Wi-Fi system. Care to explain?

Mira's eyes dart back and forth, her brain scrambling for a way out. Then—her expression hardens. She lets out a sharp laugh, shaking her head.

MIRA (cold, smirking again): This is pathetic. If I was behind any of this, why would I be dumb enough to use the school's Wi-Fi?

ALEXIA (coolly, setting down another sheet): Because you were too arrogant to think you'd get caught. Silence.

Mira's fingers dig into her chair. Alexia watches as, for the first time, Mira has nothing to say.

(Principal Ward exhales, rubbing his temples.

PRINCIPAL WARD (serious, looking at Mira): Mira, I'm extremely disappointed. This is beyond a student council campaign. This is cyber harassment, and it won't be tolerated.

MIRA (voice shaking, clenching her fists): I didn't—

PRINCIPAL WARD (cutting in, sternly): Enough. I'll be calling your parents immediately. You will be facing consequences for this, both from the school and possibly beyond that.

Mira's face falls. She swallows hard but doesn't argue. She knows she's trapped.

Alexia lets out a breath she didn't realize she was holding. For the first time in weeks, she feels lighter.

Natalie gathers her documents, giving Alexia a small nod of approval. Alexia meets her gaze and nods back.

FADE TO BLACK.

SCRIPT 6

FADE IN:

INT. HIGH SCHOOL – SCHOOL HALLWAY – MORNING

ALEXIA stands in front of a bulletin board, carefully pinning up a campaign poster. It reads: “Vote Alexia for Student Council President! Leadership. Integrity. Change.” She steps back to admire her work.

Sam, one of her Alexia’s friends and classmates nods approvingly.

SAM: Looks good! You got this, Alexia.

ALEXIA (nervous, but excited): I’m still not sure, but... Why not, right? We can make a difference.
(hey walk away. A few moments later, MIRA and her FRIENDS approach. MIRA smirks, pulls out a marker, and draws devil horns on Alexia’s face on the poster.)

MIRA (mocking): Leadership. Integrity. Change. More like Loser. Invisible. Cringe.

Her friends laugh as they walk away.

SCENE 2 – SCHOOL HALLWAY – NEXT DAY

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Her phone buzzes. She check it to find another hateful comment on her social media: “No one wants an ugly loser like you as president.” More notifications flood in.

SAM (concerned): Alexia... this is getting bad. Maybe you tell the headmaster.

ALEXIA : I’ll talk to her.

SCENE 3 – SCHOOL CAFETERIA – AFTERNOON

The cafeteria is buzzing with students. Laughter, trays clattering, conversations overlapping. ALEXIA, holding her lunch tray, scans the room until she spots MIRA sitting at a table with her FRIENDS.

ALEXIA takes a breath and marches toward them. Students around the cafeteria begin to take notice, sensing tension in the air.

ALEXIA (firm, controlled): Mira.

Mira looks up with a smirk.

MIRA (mocking surprise): Alexia! To what I owe the honor?

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MIRA: Whoa, whoa, whoa. Accusations? Without proof? That's defamation. Maybe I should sue.

Her friends chuckle. ALEXIA sets her tray down on the table, leaning in.

ALEXIA (whispering): Why are you doing this?

Mira leans forward too, their faces inches apart. Her smile doesn't reach her eyes.

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Alexia stiffens. Mira takes a sip of her soda, looking unbothered.

MIRA : Face it, Alexia. You're not up to the task. You never were. These are the big leagues for exceptional players. You can't compete, you don't have what it takes.

She leans back, crosses her arms.

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The whole table laughs as Alexia clenches her fists. She grabs her tray and walks away, head high, but inside, she's breaking.

SCENE 4 – ALEXIA'S BEDROOM – NIGHT

Alexia sits on her bed, knees to her chest, staring at her laptop screen. Her phone buzzes again. Another notification. Another message.

She hesitates, then opens Instagram. Her stomach drops. A new post—photos of her, edited and fake. They make her look like she's shoplifting, cheating on a test, even in a mugshot. Dozens of cruel comments underneath.

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Her breath comes in shallow gasps. Her fingers tremble as she locks her phone. She swallows hard and picks it up again, dialing her mom.

MOTHER (answering, tired, background noise of hospital beeping and chatter): Hey, sweetheart, I can’t talk long. What’s up?

ALEXIA (small voice): Mom... I—something’s happening at school.

MOTHER (distracted, sighing): Alexia, I know it’s tough, but I have a twelve-hour shift. Can we talk later?

ALEXIA: Umm... sure.

MOTHER (cutting in, exhausted): I love you, honey. We’ll talk tomorrow, okay?

Click. The line goes dead. Alexia grips her phone, staring at it. A long pause. Then, she tosses it onto the bed, her eyes stinging with tears.

She looks back at her laptop. Slowly, she types: “How to report cyberbullying?” She clicks on a website, scrolls... her eyes scanning Her fingers hesitate over the keyboard. Finally, she takes a deep breath and starts typing.

SCENE 5 – SCHOOL - CLASSROOM

Alexia sits at her desk. Then—DING!—a new email notification. Her heart pounds as she clicks it open.

EMAIL RESPONSE:

"Thank you for reaching out. We understand how serious this situation is. Unfortunately, school cyberbullying cases can be difficult to prosecute without concrete proof. However, we strongly encourage you to go to the police and file a report. They can guide you on legal actions and issue warnings if necessary. Stay strong—you're not alone."

Alexia’s stomach sinks. The police? She had hoped for something more immediate, something that would stop this. But this... this feels like a dead end.

Still, she has no other options.

She closes her laptop, her body tense with exhaustion.

SCENE 6 – POLICE STATION – DAY

The police station is small and packed with people waiting—tired mothers, frustrated civilians, officers shuffling through stacks of paperwork. Phones ringing, keyboards clicking. The air smells like coffee and sweat.

Alexia stands at the front desk, gripping her phone like a lifeline. The young OFFICER behind the desk barely looks at her, typing something on his computer.

OFFICER (distracted, without looking up): What's the issue?

ALEXIA (hesitant, then firm): I need to file a cyberbullying report. Someone at my school has been spreading fake photos of me and sending me threats online.

The officer sighs, finally looking up, his expression blank

OFFICER: Do you know who is behind it?

ALEXIA (nodding quickly): It is a girl from my school—Mira. But she's using fake accounts, and I don't have direct proof that it's her.

The officer's brows furrow slightly. He glances at his already overloaded paperwork, then back at Alexia.

OFFICER (voice flat): So, you think it's her, but you don't have concrete evidence?

ALEXIA (frustrated, desperate): I have screenshots of the messages, the posts, the threats. Can't you trace the accounts? I just—I need this to stop.

The officer exhales, rubbing his temple.

OFFICER (sympathetic, but dismissive): Look, I'm really sorry you're going through this. But cyberbullying cases are complicated. We'd have to go through a long process to track the IP addresses, and even then, unless there are direct threats of violence, there's not much we can do.

ALEXIA (disbelief washing over her): So that's it? She gets away with it?

OFFICER (shrugging slightly): If it escalates into something more serious, then we might be able to act. But right now... legally, there's no solid case. The best thing you can do is block the accounts, report the posts, and try not to engage.

Alexia stares at him. The weight of his words crashes down on her.

No one is coming to help. Not the school. Not the law. No one.

Her hands shake, and she clenches her jaw, swallowing the burning lump in her throat.

ALEXIA (soft, bitter laugh): So, the law's not on my side.

OFFICER (shrugging): Not really, kid. I'm sorry.

She turns on her heel and walks out, her fists clenched. The sound of ringing phones and idle chatter fades behind her as she steps into the daylight, the harsh truth settling in.

For the first time, she truly understands—Mira was right. She could do this. And no one would stop her.

SCENE 8 – SCHOOL AUDITORIUM – ONE MONTH LATER

The auditorium is packed. Balloons and banners cover the stage. A crowd of students cheers as Mira, standing at the podium, beams with triumph.

MIRA (grinning, into the mic): Thank you all for your votes! I promise, this year will be the best one yet!

The crowd erupts in applause. Alexia sits near the back, her face unreadable as she watches Mira bask in her victory. The girl who destroyed her reputation. The girl who got away with it.

She exhales slowly, then stands and walks out of the auditorium, the cheers echoing behind her.

SCENE 9 – OFFICE OF LOCAL REPRESENTATIVE – TWO MONTHS LATER

A modest office, lined with bookshelves and old campaign posters. An OLDER MAN, mid-60s, glasses perched on his nose, sits behind a cluttered desk, flipping through a folder. Across from him sits Alexia, poised, her hands folded neatly in her lap.

The representative looks up, adjusting his glasses, giving her a puzzled look.

REPRESENTATIVE (curious, amused): A petition? About cyberbullying legislation?

ALEXIA (nods, calm but firm): 5,000 signatures. From students, teachers, parents. People who understand how serious this is.

REPRESENTATIVE (leaning back, thoughtful): You know... writing laws isn't easy. It takes time. Committees. Debate. Political will.

A pause. Alexia reaches into her bag and pulls out a neatly typed document. She places it on the desk, sliding it toward him

ALEXIA (small smile, unwavering): That's okay. I already have a draft.

The representative blinks, surprised. He looks down at the document, then back up at Alexia. A slow smile tugs at the corner of his lips.

REPRESENTATIVE (grinning, impressed): Well then. It's a start.

ALEXIA (small smile, unwavering): I know it won't be easy. Good things never are. I am willing to do whatever it takes. However long it takes.

FADE OUT.

SCRIPT 7

FADE IN:

INT. CLASSROOM – DAY

Students are preparing for gym class. Backpacks and clothes are being tossed onto chairs and desks. ANDREI (16), a Romanian student, remains at his desk, focused on his laptop. IGOR (16), his classmate, grins as he zips up his sports bag.

IGOR

(to another classmate, half joking)

Hey, maybe we shouldn't leave our stuff alone with Andrei. You know, just in case.

A beat. Some students snicker. Andrei looks up, taken aback. Igor smirks, nudging another student.

ANDREI

What?

IGOR

Relax, dude, just a joke.

Andrei forces a smile, but his expression darkens as the class exits. He sighs and resumes working, but his fingers hesitate over the keyboard.

INT. ANDREI'S HOME – EVENING

Andrei sits at the dinner table, playing with his food. His MOTHER, a warm but firm woman in her late 40s, notices his silence. She sets down her fork and studies him.

MOTHER

You're quiet. Something wrong?

ANDREI

Nothing.

MOTHER

Andrei...

Andrei exhales, putting down his fork. He hesitates before speaking.

ANDREI

It's just... at school today, Igor made a joke. About me stealing. He implied...

His mother's eyes darken.

MOTHER

Because you're Romanian?

ANDREI

Yes. But he never actually said it.

MOTHER

(scoffs)

That's not a joke. Do you want me to speak with the principal?

ANDREI

(shakes head)

No. I don't want to make a big deal out of this. It's just... I don't get it. I thought we were friends.

Mother watches him, concern etched in her face, but doesn't push further.

MOTHER

Just be careful.

INT. CLASSROOM – MORNING

Students filter in. EDY rummages through his bag, frustration growing.

EDY

Has anyone seen my credit card? It was in my bag yesterday.

Igor raises an eyebrow and smirks.

IGOR

Told you not to leave your stuff unguarded. Why don't you ask Andrei?

Some students snicker. Andrei stiffens, his face turning red.

ANDREI

(angry)

I haven't seen your card. Why would you accuse me?

IGOR

Dude, relax. It's a joke.

ANDREI

I don't think it's funny.

IGOR

Not my fault Romanians are known for stealing. If you have a problem, take it up with your fellow countrymen.

(The class falls silent. Some students exchange awkward glances. Andrei clenches his jaw, his fists tightening. The bell rings, breaking the tension.)

MONTAGE – ANDREI'S SCHOOL DAYS

- Students pointing at Andrei, whispering.
- Laughter as Andrei passes by.

INT. CLASSROOM – MORNING

Andrei opens his bag. His sunglasses are gone. He looks around, desperate.

ANDREI

Has anyone seen my sunglasses?

IGOR

(grinning)

Funny how the tables have turned. No honor among thieves, huh?

Andrei's face hardens. He lunges toward Igor, shoving his desk. Chairs screech against the floor as classmates jump back. Igor's smirk vanishes.

CLASSMATE

Whoa! Chill out!

A classmate pulls Andrei back. Andrei glares at Igor, breathing hard. Igor chuckles, but his eyes dart away.

INT. ANDREI'S BEDROOM – NIGHT

Andrei ignores his mother's worried glances at dinner. He locks himself in his room, turns on his laptop and starts watching his favourite comedy specials—Chris Rock, Gabriel Iglesias, Trevor Noah, Hasan Minhaj. His expression shifts from blank to amused, then thoughtful. An idea begins to form. His eyes light up.

EXT. SCHOOL FIELD – DAY

The school has partnered with a charity organization for a joint event. A small stage is set up for student performances. Students cheer as their friends take the stage. Then, Andrei steps up to the mic.

ANDREI

Hello, my name is Andrei and I'm... Romanian. I know, I know... but please don't hold it against me.

The audience chuckles.

ANDREI

You know, when you're Romanian, people have all these expectations. You're either a gymnast, a vampire, or apparently a professional pickpocket.

Laughter. Some students nudge each other, whispering.

ANDREI

Funny thing about it. I wasn't even aware until someone pointed it out to me.

Andrei stares Igor, who is taken aback by the unexpected turn of events. Some people applaud, others look confused/uncomfortable.

ANDREI

No, don't get me wrong, I get it. Xenophobia can be funny. Not to me or decent people, because that hilarious routine about how Romanians are thieves I think it's a bit on the nose. I mean, if you're gonna stereotype me, at least be creative! Stealing? Come on. Make me a spy! A secret agent! That way, when I take your stuff, at least it's for national security. "Mission Impossible: Romanian Edition."

Laughter. Igor crosses his arms, avoiding eye contact.

ANDREI

Now let's turn the tables. What's a xenophobe's favorite type of math? Division.

Laughter. Loud cheers. Igor slinks further down in his seat. Andrei grins.

FADE OUT.

SCRIPT 8

FADE IN:

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ANDREI

Nothing.

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(scoffs)

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ANDREI

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CLASSMATE

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CUT TO:

INT. ANDREI'S BEDROOM – NIGHT

Andrei sits at his desk, logged into his favorite online multiplayer game. He plays for a while. but is visibly distracted. A CALL pops up from his friend, DAN.

DAN (ON SCREEN)

Hey man, what's up? You're literally killing me. Where's your head at?

ANDREI

(sighs)

Sorry Dan. Jut had another crappy day.

DAN

Is it Igor?

ANDREI

Yeah! The whole thing is getting worse. I tried confronting him, but it's pointless. And going to the principal won't change anything.

DAN

(thoughtful)

Mhm... I've been thinking about this. My uncle runs a big software company. Maybe you can invite him to the class?

ANDREI

How would that help?

DAN

He has a real talent to talk to people.

ANDREI

I'm not sure.

DAN

Trust me. Worst case, nothing happens.

ANDREI

I guess. OK.

DAN

Great. I'll tell him.

INT. CLASSROOM - A WEEK LATER

The students sit at their desks as MR. SAVA, Dan's uncle, delivers his presentation.

MR. SAVA

... while I was pitching, I noticed how some investors who seemed very excited during the pitch, slightly changed their demeanor the moment I told them I was Romanian. Like suddenly "Houston, we have a problem!". At first, I didn't get it. But then... let me ask you. What do you think was their reasoning? A few students exchange glances. Someone in the back calls out—

STUDENT

Because they didn't like Romanians?

MR. SAVA

(smiling)

Some had never even met a Romanian before. So how do you know whether you like or dislike someone you've never met?

The class is silent. Andrei glances at Igor, who looks away.

MR. SAVA

It's called prejudice. Prejudice and xenophobia aren't just big words. They're the reason some people get denied opportunities. And the reason why a simple comment—just a 'joke'—can do a lot more damage than you realize.

He looks directly at Andrei. The students shift uncomfortably.

MR. SAVA

So, I've heard some of you have been making certain "jokes" lately. Let's talk about that.

MR. SAVA

Do you think a joke is still funny when it makes someone feel like they don't belong? When it makes them feel ashamed for something they can't change?

Igor shifts uncomfortably. Some students look down.

MR. SAVA

Words have weight. Words have power. A joke might feel harmless, but it spreads an idea. That idea turns into a stereotype. That stereotype builds a wall. And suddenly, a friend becomes an outsider. A classmate becomes a target. And soon, you're not just joking. You're deciding who deserves respect and who doesn't.

A beat.

MR. SAVA

Think about what you're saying. Think about what you're doing. Because prejudice isn't just about one joke—it's about the message you send, the damage you cause, whether you mean to or not.

He looks at Igor.

MR. SAVA

If someone called you a liar, over and over again, would you laugh? If people whispered behind your back, would you shrug it off?

(pauses)

You are the next generation. You get to choose—will you spread the same prejudice, or will you break the cycle? Will you carry forward the mistakes of the past or will you choose respect?

He lets his words hang. The students exchange uncertain glances. Andrei breathes in deeply.

FADE OUT.

SCRIPT 9

FADE IN:

INT. HIGH SCHOOL CLASSROOM - DAY

The classroom is buzzing with chatter. MATEI (16) sits with his best friend, DAN (16), scrolling through his phone. Across the room, ANTON (16), an autistic student, is sitting alone, focused on his notebook, tapping his fingers rhythmically on the desk.

DAN

(grinning, nudging Matei)

Look at him, man. Always tapping like a freakin' robot. Bet he's sending signals to aliens or something.

MATEI

(chuckling nervously)

Come on, Dan...

Dan smirks, gets up, and walks toward Anton, exaggeratedly mimicking his tapping.

DAN

(beeping noises)

Control tower, we have a problem! Anton the Android is malfunctioning again!

The class erupts in laughter. Anton stiffens, avoiding eye contact, shifting uncomfortably in his seat.

ANTON

(muttering)

I... I need to finish my notes. Please stop.

DAN

(mocking)

"Please stop!" Oh no, I think I hurt his circuits! What do I do, guys? Hit the reset button?

Anton grips his notebook tightly, his breathing quickens. Matei shifts in his seat but stays silent. The bell rings, ending the scene.

ONE WEEK LATER

EXT. SCHOOL COURTYARD - LUNCH BREAK

Anton is sitting on a bench, eating alone. Dan walks by with a group of students, grinning when he spots Anton.

DAN

(whispering to the group)

Watch this.

Dan walks up to Anton and suddenly grabs the sandwich from his hands.

DAN

(grinning)

Hey Anton, you don't mind sharing, right? Or do you have a special, autistic-only diet?

Anton looks down, clenching his fists. Matei, watching from a few feet away, finally steps forward.

MATEI

Dan, come on. Let him eat.

DAN

(turning to Matei)

What? It's just a joke. Chill.

MATEI

(shaking his head)

Please. Let's go.

Dan scoffs but tosses the sandwich back onto the bench. Anton picks it up quietly, his hands shaking. Dan walks off with the group, laughing. Matei looks at him for a beat, then runs after his group.

EXT. SCHOOL HALLWAY - LATER

Matei and Dan are standing by the vending machine. Dan hits it with his foot.

MATEI

Why do you mess with Anton so much?

MATEI

Yeah, but you humiliate him. Every single day.

DAN

(scoffs)

Because he's annoying. He's weird. The way he talks, the way he stares at things for too long... it's like he's not even normal. It just rubs me the wrong way.

MATEI

Yeah, but he can't help it.

DAN

Neither can I. So, I guess we're even. Let's go.

Dan takes his backpack and walks to class.

INT. MATEI'S HOME - EVENING

Matei is having dinner with his PARENTS. He pushes food around his plate, deep in thought.

MOTHER

Matei, is something wrong? You've barely touched your food.

MATEI

(sighs)

It's Dan. He keeps bullying Anton. I don't know what to do.

FATHER

(gruffly)

Stay out of it. It's not your fight.

MOTHER

(shoots father a look)

Or maybe you should rethink your friendship with Dan.

MATEI

We've been friends for years. I care about him. I just don't understand why he's like this. His mother reaches over, squeezing his hand. Matei nods, lost in thought.

INT. MATEI'S BEDROOM - NIGHT

Matei sits at his computer, typing "autism" into a search bar. He reads intently, his face shifting between curiosity and concern.

INT. SCHOOL HALLWAY - NEXT DAY

Matei walks up to Dan, handing him some printouts.

MATEI

Read this. It's about autism. Maybe it'll help you understand Anton.

Dan barely glances at the papers, scoffing.

DAN

Seriously? I don't need to read this crap.

Just then, Anton walks past. Dan smirks and steps in front of him.

DAN

So, Anton, what secret codes are you cracking today?

Matei steps between them, glaring at Dan.

MATEI

Enough, Dan.

Dan scoffs, stepping closer.

DAN

What, you're on his side now?

MATEI

I'm on the side that isn't cruel for no reason.

DAN

(scoffing)

You've changed, man.

ANTON

(softly)

Thank you.

Matei looks after Dan, sighs.

EXT. SCHOOL COURTYARD - A FEW DAYS LATER

Matei and Anton sit on a bench. Dan passes by, shooting them an angry look, but walks away. Matei watches him go.

ANTON

I'm sorry. I didn't mean to be the reason you lost your friend.

MATEI

It's not your fault, Anton. And honestly... I didn't do this just for you.

Anton frowns, confused.

ANTON

What do you mean?

MATEI

(sighs)

At first, I told myself it wasn't my problem. I wasn't the one being bullied. I wasn't the one feeling small every day. But then I started thinking. If I saw it happening, if I knew it was wrong, and still did nothing... wasn't I part of the problem?

Anton looks down, processing Matei's words.

MATEI

I kept making excuses, but that was just me trying to justify my silence. And the more I watched, the more I realized something: my silence was validating.

ANTON

You didn't have to say anything, though. No one expected you to.

MATEI

I started thinking about what it would feel like to be in your position—to have someone mock me every day, to have people laugh like my feelings didn't matter. And I realized I wouldn't want a friend like me who just stood by, letting it happen.

ANTON

But now Dan hates you.

MATEI

Yeah. That sucks. But I like myself better.

A beat of silence.

MATEI

Who knows, maybe he'll come around.

ANTON

What you did, it... means a lot. You were very brave.

Matei smiles, nudging Anton lightly on the shoulder.

MATEI

You're a good guy, Anton. And for what it's worth... I think you're braver than most of us.

Anton looks away, but there's the faintest hint of a smile on his lips. The school bell rings in.

FADE OUT.

SCRIPT 10

FADE IN:

INT. HIGH SCHOOL PHYSICS CLASS - DAY

The classroom is filled with the usual noise of students chatting as the PHYSICS TEACHER, a stern man in his 50s, hands back graded tests. He reaches CLARA (16), an average-looking, plump girl who sits beside her best friend, SABINE (16)

PHYSICS TEACHER

(smirks, handing Clara her test)

Well, Clara, good thing you're smart. You won't need your looks to fall back on.

A few students chuckle. Clara's face falls, and she lowers her gaze, gripping the test paper tightly.

SABINE

(whispering)

Ignore him. He's a fossil. Probably hasn't looked in a mirror in decades.

Clara forces a small smile, but her hands tremble slightly.

EXT. SCHOOL COURTYARD - LUNCH BREAK

Clara and Sabine walk past a group of girls at a lunch table. The girls whisper, giggle, and cast glances at Clara.

GIRL 1

(laughing)

I mean, does she even look at herself before coming to school?

GIRL 2

I heard even the cafeteria stopped serving fries because of her.

(Sabine glares at them, but Clara grabs her arm and leads her to a faraway table. Clara slumps in her seat, stabbing at her food.)

CLARA

It's so unfair! Look at them! They can eat an entire pizza and nothing, while I could starve for a week and still look like... this. And I'm not even fat and pretty like Rebel Wilson.

She gestures towards the bullies. A HANDSOME BOY sits laughing with the girls who mocked Clara earlier.

CLARA

A guy like that would never look twice at me.

SABINE

(flatly)

What would you want with him? He's a moron.

Clara sighs.

INT. CLARA'S BEDROOM - EVENING

The room is cozy, but cluttered. Clara and Sabine sit cross-legged on the bed, books open. Sabine is engrossed in her homework, but Clara is staring into the mirror, pinching at her arms.

CLARA

I hate myself. I wonder if I'll ever feel different.

SABINE

Nobody has it all. You have the smarts, but not the looks. Longterm that's not a bad deal.

CLARA

If I could trade being smart for being pretty, I'd do it in a heartbeat. If I were dumb and pretty, I'd be happy.

SABINE

Too bad you're just dumb.

Clara snorts despite herself. Sabine hits her with a pillow.

INT. SCHOOL HALLWAY - MORNING

Clara and Sabine are walking to class when a group of classmates step in their way.

GIRL 1

(grinning)

Clara, when are you gonna stop eating your feelings?

GIRL 2

Why did God make you so damn ugly girl?

The group laughs. Clara's face burns, and she looks at the ground. Sabine steps forward.

SABINE

Fudge off! Dumbasses!

The bullies laugh and walk away, still snickering.

SABINE

(turning to Clara)

Why didn't you say anything?

CLARA

What would I say? They were right. I am ugly.

SABINE

How can you say that?

CLARA

(defensive)

Just drop it, okay?

SABINE

Fine. I will.

The tension between them is thick. Sabine sighs and walks off, leaving Clara standing alone.

INT. SCHOOL HALLWAY - A WEEK LATER

Clara enters, wearing heavy makeup—too much foundation, bright lipstick, exaggerated eyeliner. The hallway erupts into laughter.

GIRL 1

Oh my God, who let her raid a clown's makeup kit?

Clara tears up and runs off.

Sabine watches from afar, frowning, but doesn't intervene.

INT. CLARA'S BEDROOM - EVENING

Sabine enters.

CLARA

Why are you here?

Sabine sits on Clara's bed and gives her a folder. Inside are printed photos and interviews of famous actors and musicians.

CLARA

(frowning)

What's this?

SABINE

Stories. Of people who were bullied in school for how they looked. But guess what? They didn't peak in high school. They bloomed later.

CLARA

(flatly)

I don't think I'll ever bloom.

SABINE

You don't get to decide that. And neither do those idiots at school. I've known you longer than they have, and I like you for who you are. Maybe, for now, that should be enough.

Clara looks at Sabine, her eyes glistening with unshed tears. She clutches the folder.)

INT. SCHOOL HALLWAY - NEXT DAY

Clara and Sabine walk side by side. The same bullies approach.

GIRL 1

Oh look, if it isn't Little Miss Science Project. Clara, are you planning to invent a potion that cures ugly?

CLARA

(loud and firm)

For you? Sure. 50 bucks. But you're ugly on the inside too, so it probably won't work.

The bullies blink, taken aback. Before they can answer back, Clara and Sabine walk away.

CLARA

That felt good.

SABINE

(grinning)

Took you long enough.

CLARA

Yeah, well... maybe I'm blooming.

FADE OUT.